

CUSTOMERS' PERCEPTION TOWARDS NEFT AND RTGS SERVICES – A STUDY ON INDIAN BANKING INDUSTRY

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Cite This Article: R. Venkatesh & D. Sangeetha, "Customers' Perception towards NEFT and RTGS Services – A Study on Indian Banking Industry", International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, Volume 2, Issue 2, Page Number 91-103, 2017.

Abstract:

The main advantage of a cashless society is that a record of all economic transactions through electronic means makes it almost impossible to sustain black market or underground economies that often prove damaging to national economies. However cash is the preferred mode of payment for those sections of society no having access to formal payment system. A slow transformation has taken place in the various sectors of society migrating financial transaction (receipts and payments) to electronic mode. This transformation will undoubtedly continue because of the universal concept of computerization and digitalization. Electronic payment is less expensive compared to payment through cash. However it is the decision in the hands of the customers. Hence it is significant to study the concept of electronic fund transfer and to measure the customers' satisfaction in order to identify the factors being satisfactory and dissatisfactory. The main aim of this research is to identify factors influencing customer satisfaction on NEFT and RTGS facilities.

Key Words: Customer perception, National Electronic Fund Transfer & Real Time Gross Settlement

1. Introduction:

Electronic money covers a wide variety of monetary transactions. The transferred money can be a credit or debit. The electronic money, also known as digital money, includes the use of computer network like internet and digital stored value systems for transactions. The financial cryptography and other related technologies are included in electronic money. The transactions are made on internet or with the help of smart cards. The roots of electronic money can be found in the increased use of computers. In 1860, the Western Union introduced the electronic fund transfer (EFT) and this marked the beginning of electronic money. Semi-Automatic Business Research Environment (SABRE) was jointly created by IBM and American Airlines. In 1964, a fully operational airline reservation system, with a real time transaction processing system, was set up by SABRE. The telephone lines were connected to the terminals fitted at the airport and reservations were done on the basis of credit, for the first time in history. In 1970, all branches of the banks in Europe were linked using mainframes. France witnessed the use of electronic money, with the introduction of the Mintel services. The French Mintel terminals were given free of cost to everybody so that they could use these terminals for online shopping.

In late 1990s, the technologies related to electronic money like electronic checks and embedded smart cards used the public key cryptography for transferring money. With the advent of e-mail, the transactions of electronic money started increasing. People started sending their credit card details via e-mail to buy goods. Later, the customers started having an online account to avoid transaction fees. Nowadays, the use of electronic money is possible due to cryptography and digital signatures. Public key encryption and decryption together are called public key cryptography. The public key encryption involves two keys, viz. public key and private key to authenticate the identity of an entity, electronically. As the name suggests, the public key is published and the private key is kept secret. Data is encrypted with the public key and the same data is decrypted with the corresponding private key. Digital signatures are used when you are encrypting some important information that is to be kept confidential. Digital signatures involve the use of hash tables that encrypt a hash are using the private key and decrypt the hash using the private key. This technique changed the tangible cash to electronic cash and is hassle free. Two types of electronic cash are direct deposit and electronic fund transfer (EFT). The debit cards and online payment of bill help in easy and quick transfer of money. However, there are a few disadvantages of electronic money. Frauds and system failures are the significant drawbacks of electronic cash. The hacking of personal banking accounts are observed frequently in these years. Failure of software and power loss can sometime prove dangerous when transferring money electronically. Although there are disadvantages, steps are taken to decrease these malpractices. Electronic money has surely changed the business and banking techniques. Electronic money has enabled.

National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT):

National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) is one of the most prominent electronic funds transfer system of India. Started in November 2005, NEFT is a facility provided to bank customers to enable them to transfer funds easily and securely on a one-to-one basis. It is done via electronic messages. This is not on real-time basis like RTGS (Real Time Gross Settlement). This is a "net" transfer facility which is executed in hourly

batches resulting in a time lag. NEFT facilities are available in 30,000 bank branches all over the country and work on a batch mode. RBI explains this scheme as "National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) is a nationwide payment system facilitating one-to-one funds transfer. Under this Scheme, individuals, firms and corporate can electronically transfer funds from any bank branch to any individual, firm or corporate having an account with any other bank branch in the country participating in the Scheme. NEFT has gained popularity due to its saving on time and the ease with which the transactions can be concluded, This reflects from the fact that 42% of all electronic transactions in the 2008 financial year were NEFT transactions.

Settlement Timings:

Currently, NEFT operates in hourly batches - there are eleven settlements from 9:00 AM to 7:00 PM on week days and five settlements from 10 am to 1 pm on Saturdays. Any transaction initiated after a designated settlement time would have to wait till the next designated settlement time. As of 2013, all transactions initiated before 5 PM will be settled on same day. No transactions are settled on weekly holidays and public holidays. Transaction Timings for NEFT, Monday to Saturday (Except 2nd and 4th Saturday) is 8:00 AM to 6:30 PM. RTGS / NEFT is not allowed on Sundays, second and fourth Saturday of the month and the declared bank holidays for the calendar year.

In order to make a remittance via NEFT, the customer initiating the transfer needs to have the IFSC (Indian Financial System Code) of the bank branch where the beneficiary account is located. IFSC is an alphanumeric 11-digit code that functions as a unique address for a particular branch. Customers will also need to input the beneficiary account number and name as well as the name of the bank being transferred to.

Benefits of NEFT:

- ✓ Safe and Effective – For a seamless movement of funds on the Internet, you could opt for NEFT as it helps you transfer any amount of money quickly.
- ✓ Low Processing Charges – Internet banking and NEFT are flexible payment options which are very economical. For getting this facility, you don't have to reimburse a huge sum of money to your bank. The processing charges are quite low and you can transfer any amount of money without any difficulty.
- ✓ Highly Dependable – NEFT, an integral aspect of Internet banking, is a highly dependable method of making payments and receiving funds online. Most of the banks in India are regulated under the norms set by RBI and, hence, the Internet banking facility too is quite safe in nature.
- ✓ Rapid Settlement – Unlike the regular banking methods of fund transfer, NEFT transfer is really quick and you can enjoy rapid settlement of accounts, thereby improving the overall functionality of your business.

Disadvantages of NEFT:

- ✓ Highly Technical – One of the major drawbacks of Internet banking and NEFT transfer in India is that this is a highly technical method of funds transfer which is not easy to operate for everyone. An individual with little knowledge of computer or the Internet might not be able to operate an Internet banking account easily.
- ✓ The Risk involved with Online Payments – Even though most of the banks in India take proper steps to secure a NEFT transaction, it is quite possible that your information might get passed on to a hacker if you're using an unsecured browser. This is one of the reasons why a lot of people across the country don't believe in this facility. Even though Internet banking comes along with certain disadvantages, this is one of the best and the easiest methods of carrying out financial transactions in the country. As a customer, you should definitely give this online payment method a try.

Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS)

Real-time gross settlement Real-time gross settlement are specialist funds transfer systems where the transfer of money or securities takes place from one bank to another on a "real time" and on a "gross" basis. Settlement in "real time" means a payment transaction is not subjected to any waiting period, with transactions being settled as soon as they are processed. "Gross settlement" means the transaction is settled on one-to-one basis without bundling or netting with any other transaction. "Settlement" means that once processed, payments are final and irrevocable. RTGS systems are typically used for high-value transactions that require and receive immediate clearing. In some countries the RTGS systems may be the only way to get same day cleared funds and so may be used when payments need to be settled urgently. However, most regular payments would not use a RTGS system, but instead would use a national payment system or network that allows participants to batch and net payments. RTGS systems are usually operated by a country's central bank as it is seen as a critical infrastructure for a country's economy. Economists believe that an efficient national payment system reduces the cost of exchanging goods, and is indispensable to the functioning of the interbank, money, and capital markets. A weak payment system may severely drag on the stability and developmental capacity of a national economy; its failures can result in inefficient use of financial resources, inequitable risk-sharing among agents, actual losses for participants, and loss of confidence in the financial system and in the very use of money. Maintained or controlled by the central of a country. There is no physical exchange of money; the central bank makes adjustments in the electronic accounts of Bank A and Bank B, reducing the balance in Bank A's account by the

amount in question and increasing the balance of Bank B's account by the same amount. The RTGS system is suited for low-volume, high-value transactions. It lowers settlement risk, besides giving an accurate picture of an institution's account at any point of time. The objective of RTGS systems by central banks throughout the world is to minimize risk in high-value electronic payment settlement systems. In an RTGS system, transactions are settled across accounts held at a central bank on a continuous gross basis. Settlement is immediate, final and irrevocable. Credit risks due to settlement lags are eliminated. The best RTGS national payment systems are cover up to 95% of high-value transactions within the national monetary market. RTGS systems are an alternative to systems of settling transactions at the end of the day, also known as the net settlement system, such as the BACS system in the United Kingdom. In a net settlement system, all the inter-institution transactions during the day are accumulated, and at the end of the day, the central bank adjusts the accounts of the institutions by the net amounts of these transactions. The World Bank has been paying increasing attention to payment system development as a key component of the financial infrastructure of a country, and has provided various forms of assistance to over 100 countries. Most of the RTGS systems in place are secure and have been designed around international standards and best practices. There are several reasons for central banks to adopt RTGS. First, a decision to adopt is influenced by competitive pressure from the global financial markets. Second, it is more beneficial to adopt an RTGS system for central bank when this allows access to a broad system of other countries' RTGS systems. Third, it is very likely that the knowledge acquired through experiences with RTGS systems spills over to other central banks and helps them make their adoption decision. Fourth, central banks do not necessarily have to install and develop RTGS themselves. The possibility of sharing development with providers that have built RTGS systems in more than one country (CGI of UK, CMA Small System of Sweden, JV Pergo of South Africa and SIA SPA of Italy, Montran of USA) has presumably lowered the cost and hence made it feasible for many countries to adopt. As at 1985, three central banks had implemented RTGS systems, while by the end of 2005, RTGS systems had been implemented by 90 central banks.

Features and Characteristics of RTGS Services:

- ✓ As in the name, RTGS does transfers in "real time" and it's an ongoing process which keeps continuing throughout the banking hours simultaneously.
- ✓ RTGS also adopts a gross settling method. This means that settlement is done immediately without delay and an individual settlement is adopted based on one by one instruction basis. This is the reason why RTGS is the fastest means of money transfer that is available to the Indian people nowadays.
- ✓ Unlike NEFT, there is a lower limit of Rs.2 lakhs while making the RTGS transfers. This is done to basically filter out the traffic that the banking community sees. And only amounts above Rs.2lakhs are given the priority method of the RTGS transfers.
- ✓ RTGS transfers can be done in a similar way as that of NEFT and also by Internet banking by choosing the Inter-Bank transfer options.

Customer Benefits:

As far as pricing of the transaction is concerned, it gets well as compared to the current system of demand or bank draft, which is one of the most prevalent ways for transferring money by individual retail customer. When RTGS is fully functional, money will reach your account on Day Zero itself or the very day a demand draft is presented to a bank. At present, this process takes about three days. Not only that, the system also cuts out the risk involved in shipment of physical demand drafts. The RBI will charge a fee Rs 25 per leg of an RTGS deal, or Rs 50 for two legs - one from the bank to the RBI hub and the other from the RBI hub to the corresponding bank. One leg constitutes the transfer of a consolidated amount (value of various instruments including total cheques presented by the bank) to be cleared. Currently, the RBI does not charge any transaction fees.

The Cost to the Customer:

Banks will charge an RTGS transaction fee depending on their relationship with the customer. Bankers said prices will vary from Rs. 50 to Rs. 200 per transaction. Pricing terms could be negotiated and special offers could be given if a customer maintains a permanent account with the bank in the form of savings or current account or has housing loan or credit card facility with the specific bank. The pricing will also differ if the amount is more than Rs 1,00,000. Another reason for Indian banks to hike their fees is to make up for loss of 'float money' or interest earned while funds take up to five days to move from one account to another. You see, commercial banks clear cheques worth roughly Rs 25,000 crore (Rs 250 billion) a day and they earn 4.5 per cent annually by deploying those funds on an overnight basis. But float money will fall with the introduction of RTGS, so banks will have to recover not only the transaction fee that the RBI will be charging them, but would also have to compensate for the loss of float-based earnings. Banks, which earn an average six per cent of their total income from fees, charge retail customers between Rs 10 and Rs 20 to send Rs 10,000 to a rival bank in another city. Moreover the banks will charge a higher fee if the funds are flowing out of the bank or the customer is making a payment from his bank's account. Conversely, the fees will be less if the funds are coming into the bank.

The Advantage for Companies:

Apart from cutting down on paper work, big companies are expected to save over Rs 2,000 per Rs 1 crores (Rs 10 million) worth of transactions using RTGS, a global standard for managing fund transfers. It reduces the risk of counter-party default and boosts confidence, apart from helping companies manage their working capital requirements more effectively. In short, it allows companies to collect funds from customers and move money to and from plant sites faster.

Difference between NEFT and RTGS:

- ✓ The basic differences between them are settlement timings. RTGS is based on the gross settlement where the transaction is settled on an instruction by instruction basis. NEFT is an electronic fund transfer system that operates on a Deferred Net Settlement (DNS) basis which settles transactions in batches.
- ✓ As per the Reserve Bank of India for RTGS the minimum amount should be above Rs 2 lakh and NEFT has no limit either minimum or maximum – on the amount of funds that could be transferred using NEFT.
- ✓ RTGS is done on continuous basis whereas NEFT operates in hourly batches - there are eleven settlements from 9 a.m. to 7 p.m. on week days (Monday through Friday) and five settlements from 9 a.m. to 1 p.m. on Saturdays.

Charges applicable for the transaction
NEFT For transactions up to Rs 1 lakh – not exceeding Rs 5 (+ Service Tax) For transactions above Rs 1 lakh and up to Rs 2 lakhs – not exceeding Rs 15 (+ Service Tax) For transactions above Rs 2 lakh – not exceeding Rs 25(+ Service tax)
RTGS For transactions between Rs 2 lakh to Rs 5 lakh - not exceeding Rs. 30 per transaction.

2. Review of Literature:

Jun and Cai (2001) identified one of the very important service quality dimensions of I-banking service quality is reliability. The online banking environment has grown tremendously over the past several years and will continue to grow as financial institutions continue to strive to allow customers to complete money transfers, pay bills, and access critical information online. During this same time, online banking has been plagued by Internet criminals and fraudsters attempting to steal customer information. Phishing and other types of attacks have become well known and are widely used as a means for fraudsters to obtain information from customers and access online banking accounts.

Mohammed Sadique Khan and Siba Sankar Mahapatra (2009) in their study attempted to evaluate the service quality of internet banking services in India from customer’s perspective. The results show that customers are satisfied with quality of service on four dimensions such as reliability, accessibility, privacy/security, responsiveness and fulfillment, but least satisfied with the ‘user friendliness’ dimension. The empirical findings not only priorities different parameters but also provide guidelines to bankers to focus on the parameters on which they need to improve.

Akudo C. Anyanwu, Absalom E. Ezugwu, Sale E. Abdullahi in his study on Electronic Payment System (EPS): Facilitating the Development and Adoption in Nigeria have analyzed that parties conducting electronic businesses and transactions have usually never seen each other face-to-face, nor exchanged currency or hard copies of documents hand-to hand. The society at large prefers transactions that involve physical contact of people, cash and cheques to that which is done over a telecommunication network such as the Internet. However, security, trust and convenience are among the major contending factors affecting the adoption of e-payment systems in Nigeria. This paper presents issues on the factors necessary to facilitate the development of EPS in Nigeria and devise ways to enhance its adoption by users.

3. Need of the Study:

Normal payment system is slow and time consuming, as customer needs to wait in queue for requesting of demand draft and other banking services. In online transfer payment from one any branch of any bank is made in the shortest time. If the customers are not fully aware about these services, they may not be able to use it. In the wake of increasing customers’ awareness, the present study is undertaken to know about the factors responsible for utilizing these services and to find out satisfaction level of customer and associating problems.

3. Statement of Problem:

Every time the users need to perform some transactions, we has to go to bank in person and do our necessary work, which may not be so feasible all the time, it may be a hard and hitting task for the users and bankers too. Online banking system provides enhanced techniques for maintaining the required information up-to date which results in efficiency and customer’s transactions are made easy when they adopt E-banking system. Client satisfaction is a serious issue for the success of any organization. Service quality is the main indicator to measure the client satisfaction. The relation between Service quality and client satisfaction are very important in business especially in service industry. In the modern environments, providing high service quality

is the major key for a sustainable competitive advantage. Being in an industry catering to the millions, banks are constantly offering new products to satisfy their diverse client bases with varied tastes and preferences. In recent years, internet banking is one of the facilities are offering to their clients to ensure client satisfaction along with improved business. The internet banking or online banking is a win-win solution for both the banks and their clients (Ray & Bhattacharya 2016). The clients are advantaged because of the convenience, flexibility and literally 24-hour banking solutions in their hands and the banks get benefitted because of lower operating costs, wider geographical reach and reduced client pressure on their branches. Present status of Indian commercial banks demonstrates that maximum amount of branches are computerized and with CBS (Core Banking Solution). Commercial banks working in rural areas also providing most of internet banking services like mobile banking, NEFT, RTGS, ATM, credit cards, POS etc. Basically e-banking includes all non-traditional and electronic means of banking such as ATM, internet banking (IB), mobile banking, banking through credit cards and debit cards etc.

4. Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the problems faced by the NEFT and RTGS Services users.
- ✓ To analyze the reasonable factors for using NEFT and RTGS Services.
- ✓ To analyze the satisfaction level of customer towards NEFT and RTGS Services.

5. Hypothesis:

- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the Education Qualification of respondents and their factor influencing to use NEFT Services.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the Education Qualification of respondents and their factor influencing to use RTGS Services.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the Education Qualification of respondents and their problem faced by NEFT Services.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the Education Qualification of respondents and their problem faced by RTGS Services.

6. Research Methodology:

Customers require the bank’s services for 24 hours. Now in this modern age the entire banking structure has been changed due to widespread internet technology. Now all the business like commerce, trade, import, export, purchase and sale of goods is relying upon electronic banking by using the advanced electronic technology the banking services are fast and economical. In this context this study focus on Determinant of customers perception towards NEFT and RTGS Services. Primary data the actual information which is received by the researcher for study from the actual field of research. In this study, primary data was collected from structured questionnaire. In this study, the researcher adopted convenience sampling. The sample size of the study was 100 respondents in the Coimbatore District. The data collected through structured questionnaires. The collected data were recorded, analyzed and interpreted in the significant manner with the help of SPSS package. The statistical tools used for the study included Simple percentage method and One way ANOVA test.

7. Data Analysis:

Table 1

Reason for Choosing the Bank for NEFT Services					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Quick and Convenient	43	43.0	43.0	43.0
	Excellent Services offered by this bank	14	14.0	14.0	57.0
	Brand Name of the bank	3	3.0	3.0	60.0
	Time Saving	40	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

From the above table found that 43 percentage of the respondents are choosing the bank for NEFT services for quick and convenient, 14 percentage of the respondents are choosing the bank for NEFT services for excellent services offered by bank, 3 percentage of the respondents are choosing the bank for NEFT services for due to brand name of the bank and 40 percentage of the respondents are choosing the bank for NEFT services for time saving. Hence the majority of 43 percentage respondents are choosing the bank for NEFT services for quick and convenient.

Table 2

Reason for Choosing the Bank for RTGS Services					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Quick and Convenient	26	26.0	26.0	26.0
	Excellent Services offered by this bank	15	15.0	15.0	41.0
	Brand Name of the bank	15	15.0	15.0	56.0

	Time Saving	44	44.0	44.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

From the above table found that 26 percentage of the respondents are choosing the bank for RTGS services for quick and convenient, 15 percentage of the respondents are choosing the bank for RTGS services for excellent services offered by bank, 15 percentage of the respondents are choosing the bank for RTGS services for due to brand name of the bank and 44 percentage of the respondents are choosing the bank for NEFT services for time saving. Hence the majority of 44 percentage respondents are choosing the bank for NEFT services for time saving.

Table 3

Purpose of using NEFT Services					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	For Business Transactions	11	11.0	11.0	11.0
	For Personal Transactions	38	38.0	38.0	49.0
	For Both	51	51.0	51.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

From the above table reveals that 11 percentage of the respondents are using NEFT services for business transaction, 38 percentage of the respondents are using NEFT services for personal transactions and 51 percentage of the respondents are using NEFT services for both business and personal transactions. Hence the majority of 51 percentage respondents are using NEFT services for both business and personal transactions.

Table 4

Purpose of using RTGS Services					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	For Business Transactions	27	27.0	27.0	27.0
	For Personal Transactions	41	41.0	41.0	68.0
	For Both	32	32.0	32.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the above table reveals that 27 percentage of the respondents are using RTGS services for business transaction, 41 percentage of the respondents are using RTGS services for personal transactions and 32 percentage of the respondents are using RTGS services for both business and personal transactions. Hence the majority of 41 percentage respondents are using RTGS services for personal transactions.

Table 5

ANOVA test for Education Qualification of respondents and their factor influencing to use NEFT Services						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Convenient and quick transaction	Between Groups	5.118	4	1.279	2.793	.031
	Within Groups	43.522	95	.458		
	Total	48.640	99			
More transparent mechanism	Between Groups	13.280	4	3.320	7.941	.000
	Within Groups	39.720	95	.418		
	Total	53.000	99			
Fully secured and reliable	Between Groups	8.603	4	2.151	2.716	.034
	Within Groups	75.237	95	.792		
	Total	83.840	99			
Reduce credit risk	Between Groups	2.147	4	.537	.498	.737
	Within Groups	102.413	95	1.078		
	Total	104.560	99			
Better option than Demand Draft or cheque	Between Groups	6.420	4	1.605	2.370	.058
	Within Groups	64.330	95	.677		
	Total	70.750	99			
Facilities of CRM	Between Groups	18.349	4	4.587	4.266	.003
	Within Groups	102.161	95	1.075		
	Total	120.510	99			
Low service charges	Between Groups	7.261	4	1.815	2.586	.042

	Within Groups	66.699	95	.702		
	Total	73.960	99			
Co-operative personnel	Between Groups	2.172	4	.543	.892	.472
	Within Groups	57.828	95	.609		
	Total	60.000	99			
Technical knowledge and awareness	Between Groups	3.893	4	.973	.793	.533
	Within Groups	116.667	95	1.228		
	Total	120.560	99			
Avail by every customer	Between Groups	7.801	4	1.950	1.579	.186
	Within Groups	117.359	95	1.235		
	Total	125.160	99			
Easy to operate	Between Groups	4.042	4	1.010	.640	.636
	Within Groups	150.068	95	1.580		
	Total	154.110	99			
Can be operated through internet banking	Between Groups	8.846	4	2.211	1.912	.115
	Within Groups	109.904	95	1.157		
	Total	118.750	99			
All A/C holders can be operate	Between Groups	23.979	4	5.995	6.578	.000
	Within Groups	86.581	95	.911		
	Total	110.560	99			
Transaction timing	Between Groups	3.699	4	.925	1.068	.377
	Within Groups	82.261	95	.866		
	Total	85.960	99			
Good customer service	Between Groups	5.872	4	1.468	1.236	.301
	Within Groups	112.878	95	1.188		
	Total	118.750	99			
Competent employees	Between Groups	12.271	4	3.068	2.004	.100
	Within Groups	145.439	95	1.531		
	Total	157.710	99			
Technology awareness and knowledge	Between Groups	1.482	4	.371	.249	.909
	Within Groups	141.268	95	1.487		
	Total	142.750	99			

Source: Output Generated from SPSS 19

Based on result generated from SPSS 19, the significant some value of the respondents are respect of Convenient and quick transaction, More transparent mechanism, Fully secured and reliable, Facilities of CRM, Low service charges and All A/C holders can be operate are less than 0.05. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is a significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents are respect of Convenient and quick transaction, more transparent mechanism, fully secured and reliable, Facilities of CRM, Low service charges and All A/C holders can be operate.

The other significant value of respondents in respect of the Reduce credit risk, Better option than Demand Draft or cheque, Co-operative personnel, Technical knowledge and awareness, Avail by every customer, Easy to operate, Can be operated through internet banking, Transaction timing, Good customer services, Competent employees, Technology awareness and knowledge are greater than 0.05.the null hypothesis accepted. Hence there is no significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents and respect of the Reduce credit risk, Better option than Demand Draft or cheque, Co-operative personnel, Technical knowledge and awareness, Avail by every customer, Easy to operate, Can be operated through internet banking, Transaction timing, Good customer services, competent employees, Technology awareness and knowledge.

Table 6

ANOVA test for Education Qualification of respondents and their factor influencing to use RTGS Services						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Convenient and quick transaction	Between Groups	10.043	4	2.511	3.398	.012
	Within Groups	70.197	95	.739		
	Total	80.240	99			
More transparent mechanism	Between Groups	1.542	4	.385	.544	.704
	Within Groups	67.368	95	.709		
	Total	68.910	99			
Fully secured	Between Groups	18.515	4	4.629	3.049	.021

and reliable	Within Groups	144.235	95	1.518		
	Total	162.750	99			
Reduce credit risk	Between Groups	9.471	4	2.368	1.696	.157
	Within Groups	132.639	95	1.396		
	Total	142.110	99			
Better option than Demand Draft or cheque	Between Groups	13.418	4	3.355	2.925	.025
	Within Groups	108.942	95	1.147		
	Total	122.360	99			
Facilities of CRM	Between Groups	1.032	4	.258	.320	.864
	Within Groups	76.608	95	.806		
	Total	77.640	99			
Low service charges	Between Groups	6.464	4	1.616	2.087	.089
	Within Groups	73.576	95	.774		
	Total	80.040	99			
Co-operative personnel	Between Groups	1.469	4	.367	.359	.837
	Within Groups	97.281	95	1.024		
	Total	98.750	99			
Technical knowledge and awareness	Between Groups	3.581	4	.895	1.026	.398
	Within Groups	82.929	95	.873		
	Total	86.510	99			
Avail by every customer	Between Groups	20.297	4	5.074	4.387	.003
	Within Groups	109.893	95	1.157		
	Total	130.190	99			
Easy to operate	Between Groups	2.940	4	.735	.596	.666
	Within Groups	117.100	95	1.233		
	Total	120.040	99			
Can be operated through internet banking	Between Groups	1.749	4	.437	.340	.850
	Within Groups	122.211	95	1.286		
	Total	123.960	99			
All A/C holders can be operate	Between Groups	7.331	4	1.833	3.308	.014
	Within Groups	52.629	95	.554		
	Total	59.960	99			
Transaction timing	Between Groups	2.879	4	.720	.742	.565
	Within Groups	92.111	95	.970		
	Total	94.990	99			
Good customer service	Between Groups	12.501	4	3.125	4.312	.003
	Within Groups	68.859	95	.725		
	Total	81.360	99			
Competent employees	Between Groups	2.280	4	.570	.895	.470
	Within Groups	60.480	95	.637		
	Total	62.760	99			
Technology awareness and knowledge	Between Groups	8.247	4	2.062	1.787	.138
	Within Groups	109.593	95	1.154		
	Total	117.840	99			

Source: Output Generated from SPSS 19

Based on result generated from SPSS 19, the significant some value of the respondents are respect of Convenient and quick transaction, Fully secured and reliable, Better option than Demand Draft or cheque, Avail by every customer, All A/C holders can be operate and Good customer services are less than 0.05. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is a significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents are respect of Convenient and quick transaction, Fully secured and reliable, Better option than Demand Draft or cheque, Avail by every customer, All A/C holders can be operate and Good customer service.

The other significant value of respondents in respect of the More transparent mechanism, Reduce credit risk, Facilities of CRM, Low service charges, Co-operative personnel, Technical knowledge and awareness, Easy to operate, Can be operated through internet banking, Transaction timing, Competent employees and Technology awareness and knowledge are greater than 0.05.the null hypothesis accepted. Hence there is no significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents and respect of the More transparent mechanism, Reduce credit risk, Facilities of CRM, Low service charges, Co-operative personnel, Technical

knowledge and awareness, Easy to operate, Can be operated through internet banking, Transaction timing, Competent employees and Technology awareness and knowledge.

Table 7

ANOVA test for Education Qualification of respondents and their problem faced by NEFT Services						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Funds transferred but not credited to receiver	Between Groups	4.746	4	1.187	.733	.571
	Within Groups	153.694	95	1.618		
	Total	158.440	99			
Lack of awareness	Between Groups	6.622	4	1.656	1.285	.281
	Within Groups	122.378	95	1.288		
	Total	129.000	99			
Problems of leased line, routers modem and search engine	Between Groups	5.919	4	1.480	1.176	.326
	Within Groups	119.521	95	1.258		
	Total	125.440	99			
Hanging of servers that lead to delayed transaction	Between Groups	12.066	4	3.017	2.339	.061
	Within Groups	122.494	95	1.289		
	Total	134.560	99			
Issues of Security and hacker	Between Groups	4.592	4	1.148	.872	.484
	Within Groups	125.048	95	1.316		
	Total	129.640	99			
complex and technical process to carry out	Between Groups	6.809	4	1.702	1.180	.325
	Within Groups	137.031	95	1.442		
	Total	143.840	99			
Service or hidden charges	Between Groups	10.800	4	2.700	2.551	.044
	Within Groups	100.560	95	1.059		
	Total	111.360	99			
CRM and grievance issue	Between Groups	5.795	4	1.449	1.349	.258
	Within Groups	102.045	95	1.074		
	Total	107.840	99			
Lack of update and delayed information	Between Groups	6.196	4	1.549	.858	.492
	Within Groups	171.444	95	1.805		
	Total	177.640	99			
Entry of IFSC code	Between Groups	5.257	4	1.314	.755	.557
	Within Groups	165.303	95	1.740		
	Total	170.560	99			

Source: Output Generated from SPSS 19

Based on result generated from SPSS 19, the significant some value of the respondents are respect of Service or hidden charges are less than 0.05. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is a significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents are respect of Service or hidden charges.

The other significant value of respondents in respect of the Funds transferred but not credited to receiver, Lack of awareness, Problems of leased line, routers modem and search engine, Hanging of servers that lead to delayed transaction, Issues of Security and hacker, complex and technical process to carry out, Service or hidden charges, CRM and grievance issue, Enter of IFSC code are greater than 0.05.the null hypothesis accepted. Hence there is no significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents and respect of the Funds transferred but not credited to receiver, Lack of awareness, Problems of leased line, routers modem and search engine, Hanging of servers that lead to delayed transaction, Issues of Security and hacker, complex and technical process to carry out, Service or hidden charges, CRM and grievance issue, Enter of IFSC code.

Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis Ho: There is no significant relationship between the Education Qualification of respondents and their problem faced by RTGS Services.

Alternative Hypothesis H1: T here is significant relationship between the Education Qualification of respondents and their problem faced by RTGS Services.

Table 8

ANOVA test for Education Qualification of respondents and their problem faced by RTGS Services						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Funds transferred but not credited to receiver	Between Groups	4.008	4	1.002	.622	.648
	Within Groups	152.952	95	1.610		
	Total	156.960	99			
Lack of awareness	Between Groups	3.855	4	.964	1.183	.323
	Within Groups	77.385	95	.815		
	Total	81.240	99			
Problems of leased line, routers modem and search engine	Between Groups	6.236	4	1.559	1.445	.225
	Within Groups	102.524	95	1.079		
	Total	108.760	99			
Hanging of servers that lead to delayed transaction	Between Groups	1.261	4	.315	.243	.913
	Within Groups	123.249	95	1.297		
	Total	124.510	99			
Issues of Security and hacker	Between Groups	9.337	4	2.334	1.889	.119
	Within Groups	117.413	95	1.236		
	Total	126.750	99			
complex and technical process to carry out	Between Groups	4.513	4	1.128	.708	.588
	Within Groups	151.327	95	1.593		
	Total	155.840	99			
Service or hidden charges	Between Groups	7.084	4	1.771	1.169	.329
	Within Groups	143.906	95	1.515		
	Total	150.990	99			
CRM and grievance issue	Between Groups	11.539	4	2.885	1.969	.106
	Within Groups	139.211	95	1.465		
	Total	150.750	99			
Lack of update and delayed information	Between Groups	3.575	4	.894	.502	.734
	Within Groups	169.175	95	1.781		
	Total	172.750	99			
Entry of IFSC code	Between Groups	13.201	4	3.300	2.775	.031
	Within Groups	112.989	95	1.189		
	Total	126.190	99			

Source: Output Generated from SPSS 19

Based on result generated from SPSS 19, the significant some value of attitudes of the RTGS customers in respect of Enter of IFSC code are less than 0.05. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is a significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents in respect of Enter of IFSC code.

The other significant value of respondents in respect of the Funds transferred but not credited to receiver, Lack of awareness, Problems of leased line, routers modem and search engine, Hanging of servers that lead to delayed transaction, Issues of Security and hacker, complex and technical process to carry out, Service or hidden charges, Service or hidden charges, CRM and grievance issue are greater than 0.05. the null hypothesis accepted. Hence there is no significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents and respect of the Funds transferred but not credited to receiver, Lack of awareness, Problems of leased line, routers modem and search engine, Hanging of servers that lead to delayed transaction, Issues of Security and hacker, complex and technical process to carry out, Service or hidden charges, Service or hidden charges, CRM and grievance issue.

8. Findings of the Study:

- ✓ The majority of 52 percentage respondents are male. The majority of 58 percentage respondents are age group is in between 18-27 years. The majority of 46 percentage respondents are educational qualification is master degree. The majority of 64 percentage respondents are marital status is unmarried. The majority of 46 percentage respondents are occupation is private job.
- ✓ The majority of 54 percentage respondents are monthly salary is Rs.5,001- Rs.20,000. The majority of 66 percentage respondents are living in nuclear family. The majority of 80 percentage respondents are having saving account. The majority of 100 percentage respondents are aware about the NEFT

services. The majority of 100 percentage respondents are aware about the RTGS services. The majority of 40 percentage respondents were aware about NEFT services through banks. The majority of 37 percentage respondents are aware about RTGS services through banks.

- ✓ The majority of 43 percentage respondents are reason for choosing the bank for NEFT services as it is Quick and convenient. The majority of 44 percentage respondents are reason for choosing the bank for NEFT services as it is time saving. The majority of 51 percentage respondents are purpose of using NEFT services for both business and personal transactions. The majority of 41 percentage respondents are purpose of using RTGS services for personal transactions. The majority of 35 percentage respondents are time span of using NEFT services 2-5 years. The majority of 54 percentage respondents are time span of using NEFT services Less than 2 years.
- ✓ The majority of 52 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards convenient and quick transactions in NEFT services. The majority of 58 percentage respondents are satisfied towards more transparent mechanism in NEFT services. The majority of 48 percentage respondents are satisfied towards fully secured and reliable in NEFT services. The majority of 44 percentage respondents are satisfied towards reduce credit risk in NEFT services. The majority of 45 percentage respondents are very satisfied with better option than demand draft or cheque in NEFT services. The majority of 44 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards facilities of CRM in NEFT services. The majority of 38 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards low services in NEFT. The majority of 56 percentage respondents are satisfied towards co-operative personnel in NEFT services. The majority of 35 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards technical knowledge and awareness in NEFT services. The majority of 34 percentage respondents are satisfied with NEFT services are avail by every customers. The majority of 33 percentage respondents are satisfied with easy to operate in NEFT services. The majority of 37 percentage respondents are satisfied towards NEFT services can be operated through internet banking. The majority of 34 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards all account holders can be operated NEFT services. The majority of 48 percentage respondents are satisfied towards transaction timing in NEFT services. The majority of 37 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards good customer service in NEFT. The majority of 35 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards competent employees in NEFT. The majority of 49 percentage respondents are satisfied towards technology awareness and knowledge in NEFT.
- ✓ The majority of 40 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards convenient and quick transactions in RTGS services. The majority of 49 percentage respondents are satisfied towards more transparent mechanism in RTGS services. The majority of 42 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards fully secured and reliable in RTGS services. The majority of 37 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards reduce credit risk in RTGS services. The majority of 45 percentage respondents are satisfied with better option than demand draft or cheque in RTGS services. The majority of 52 percentage respondents are satisfied towards facilities of CRM in RTGS services. The majority of 46 percentage respondents are satisfied towards low services in RTGS. The majority of 46 percentage respondents are satisfied towards co-operative personnel in RTGS services. The majority of 49 percentage respondents are satisfied towards technical knowledge and awareness in RTGS services. The majority of 37 percentage respondents are very satisfied with RTGS services are avail by every customers. The majority of 46 percentage respondents are satisfied with easy to operate in RTGS services. The majority of 46 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards RTGS services can be operated through internet banking. The majority of 46 percentage respondents are satisfied towards all account holders can be operated RTGS services. The majority of 37 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards transaction timing in RTGS services. The majority of 39 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards good customer service in RTGS. The majority of 52 percentage respondents are satisfied towards competent employees in RTGS. The majority of 39 percentage respondents are very satisfied towards technology awareness and knowledge in RTGS.
- ✓ The majorities of 26 percentage respondents are neither agree nor disagree and agree towards funds transferred but not credited to receiver in NEFT services. The majority of 36 percentage respondents are neither agree nor disagree towards lack of awareness in NEFT services. The majority of 38 percentage respondents are neither agree nor disagree towards problems of leased line, routers modem and search engine in NEFT services. The majority of 30 percentage respondents are neither agree nor disagree towards hanging of servers that lead to delayed transaction in NEFT services. The majority of 30 percentage respondents are neither agree nor disagree towards issues of security and hacker in NEFT services. The majority of 40 percentage respondents are neither agree nor disagree towards complex and technical process to carry out NEFT services. The majority of 42 percentage respondents are neither agree nor disagree towards Service or hidden charges in NEFT services. The majority of 40 percentage respondents are neither agree nor disagree towards CRM and grievance issue in NEFT services. The majorities of 32 percentage respondents are agree towards lack of update and delayed

information in NEFT services. The majority of 28 percentage respondents are agreeing towards entry of IFSC code in NEFT services.

- ✓ The majorities of 37 percentage respondents are neither agree nor disagree towards funds transferred but not credited to receiver in RTGS services. The majority of 44 percentage respondents are agreeing towards lack of awareness in RTGS services. Hence the majority of 38 percentage respondents neither agrees nor disagree towards problems of leased line, routers modem and search engine in RTGS services. The majorities of 32 percentage respondents are neither agree nor disagree towards hanging of servers that lead to delayed transaction in RTGS services. The majorities of 34 percentage respondents neither agree nor disagree towards issues of security and hacker in NEFT services. The majority of 29 percentage respondents are agree towards complex and technical process to carry out in RTGS services. The majority of 30 percentage respondent are neither agree nor disagree towards Service or hidden charges in RTGS services. The majority of 25 percentage respondents are neither agree nor disagree and agree towards CRM and grievance issue in RTGS services. The majorities of 30 percentage respondents are strongly disagree towards lack of update and delayed information in RTGS services. The majority of 41 percentage respondents are disagreeing towards entry of IFSC code in RTGS services.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents are respect of Convenient and quick transaction, more transparent mechanism, fully secured and reliable, Facilities of CRM, Low service charges and All A/C holders can be operate. There is no significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents and respect of the Reduce credit risk, Better option than Demand Draft or cheque, Co-operative personnel, Technical knowledge and awareness, Avail by every customer, Easy to operate, Can be operated through internet banking, Transaction timing, Good customer services, competent employees, Technology awareness and knowledge.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents are respect of Convenient and quick transaction, Fully secured and reliable, Better option than Demand Draft or cheque, Avail by every customer, All A/C holders can be operate and Good customer service. There is no significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents and respect of the More transparent mechanism, Reduce credit risk, Facilities of CRM, Low service charges, Co-operative personnel, Technical knowledge and awareness, Easy to operate, Can be operated through internet banking, Transaction timing, competent employees and Technology awareness and knowledge.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents are respect of Service or hidden charges. There is no significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents and respect of the Funds transferred but not credited to receiver, Lack of awareness, Problems of leased line, routers modem and search engine, Hanging of servers that lead to delayed transaction, Issues of Security and hacker, complex and technical process to carry out, Service or hidden charges, CRM and grievance issue, Enter of IFSC code.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents in respect of Enter of IFSC code. There is no significant relationship between education qualifications of the respondents and respect of the Funds transferred but not credited to receiver, Lack of awareness, Problems of leased line, routers modem and search engine, Hanging of servers that lead to delayed transaction, Issues of Security and hacker, complex and technical process to carry out, Service or hidden charges, Service or hidden charges, CRM and grievance issue.

9. Suggestions:

- ✓ Banks must create awareness on the usage of electronic fund transfer through social media and campaign at rural areas to increase the usage of RTGS/NEFT facilities, as it is still unnoticed by many customers.
- ✓ Charges levied by private sector banks for using electronic fund transfer facility is more compared to public sector banks and thus make a difference in the level of satisfaction in private sector banks. It is suggested to the private sector banks to charge fairly lesser rate to attract customers.
- ✓ Bankers should encourage the current account holders to access electronic fund transfer facility to avoid delay in payment and to reduce risk in carrying paper currency.
- ✓ It is found that Lack of Awareness is considered as the major problem faced by NEFT and RTGS customers. Hence, it is suggested that the banking authorities may try to extend the awareness level of customers through TV and Newspaper advertisements, through demos by special persons appointed for this purpose etc.
- ✓ It is found that quick transactions are the major factor influencing the customer to use NEFT and RTGS services. Hence, it is suggested that the banking authorities may try to maintain the present momentum and avoid any unnecessary delays in payment settlements, if any.

- ✓ It is found that there is a significant relationship between marital status of NEFT and RTGS customers and their awareness level. Hence, it is suggested that the banking authorities may have to give importance to the marital status of their customers and try to satisfy their desires.
- ✓ It is found that higher minimum amount of remittance is considered as the second major problem faced by the NEFT and RTGS customers. Hence, it is suggested that the banking authorities may try to reduce the minimum limit (Rs.1 lakh) to certain extent which would definitely favour the growth of this speed and efficient payment settlement system.
- ✓ The banks should emphasize more on popularizing internet usage by customers which results into improvement in customer satisfaction and also cost reduction.

10. Conclusion:

The results of the current study have some implementation for banking authorities. If these factors are timely considered, it would be profitable to the banks and can help to make it more popularize this unique transaction system. It is observed that lack of awareness is considered as the major problem faced by RTGS/NEFT customers. So it is suggested that banking authorities should make an attempt to increase outreach of these services through media and personnel visit. It is also identified that convenient and quick transaction is the major influencing factor. Therefore banks should maintain the expectation of the customers and can make it more popular among business firms and individuals. Finally it is found the significant relationship between marital status and level of awareness so it is suggested that the banking personnel should give immediate attention in order to satisfy their need.

11. References:

1. Akudo C. Anyanwu, Absalom E. Ezugwu, Sale E. Abdullahi, (2012). Electronic Payment System (EPS): Facilitating the Development and Adoption in Nigeria, *International Journal of Computer Science Issues*, Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp.462-467.
2. Damodaran, M Former Chairman, SEBI, New Delhi, Report Of The Committee On Customer Service In Banks, Reserve Bank Of India Mumbai, Memorandum published on May 26, 2010, page no. 103
3. Divya Singhal, & Padmanabhan, V., (2008). A study on customer perception towards internet banking: Identifying major contributing factors. *The Journal of Nepalese Business Studies*, 5(1), 101-111
4. Gupta. S.L. "Marketing Research", Excel books, New Delhi, 2003
5. Jun.M and Cai S. (2001) The Key Determinants of Internet bank Service Quality: A Content Analysis, *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 19(7), 276-291.
6. Mohammed Sadique khan and Siba Sankar Mahapatra (2009). "Service quality evaluation in internet banking: an empirical study in India; In J. Indian culture and Business management, vol.2, No.1.
7. Natarajan, and Paresmeswaran, R., Indian Banking Chand Company Ltd, New Delhi 2007
8. Sharma D.D "Marketing research particples application and cased," sultan chandandsons, New Delhi 2002.
9. Sharma S.C., & Singh, J., (1993). "Quality of customer service, In Banks: A comparative study of SCB and PNB, Radha publication: New Delhi.
10. Single, R., & Malhotra, (1993).customer satisfaction in banking services, Radhapublication, New Delhi.
11. Srivastavasaurabh, (2009). "Internet banking –A Global way to bank". Report on trendand Progress of Indian Banking 2007-08 (RBI Bulletin).
12. Suneja, H. R., (1994). Innovations in Banking Services, Himalaya Publishing House, pp.1-20.
13. Venkatesh, R (2015). Investors Perception towards Investment in Mutual Funds - A Study in Thanjavur District. *Global Journal for Research Analysis*, Vol.1, pp. 40 – 41.
14. Venkatesh, R & Sathiya Priya, P., (2017). Impact of Demonetization on Retail Outlets – An Analytical Study, *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education*, Vol. 2, Issue 2, pp.96-105